

**THEORETICAL AND PRACTICAL ROLES OF MEDIA INFORMATION
AND COMMUNICATION IN INTERNATIONAL AND GLOBAL
CONTEXTS**

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Abstract

The world of today is defined as being “a global village”, where information and communications flow seamlessly without the barriers of distance, space and time. This essay analyses the theoretical and practical roles of media information communication in international and global contexts. It also examines a variety of theories that address the underlying principles of international connectivity within media properties. This paper is informed by the need articulate and appreciate the theoretical and practical roles of media information and communication in international and global context. The theoretical and practical roles of the media were randomly selected as unit of analysis. Findings revealed that information and communication across borders contribute majorly to the socio-cultural, political, and economic global spheres in many ways. The world economy is connected, e-commerce and international trade have advanced, and financial markets have become more linked. Furthermore, global popular culture and new types of societies have emerged. Nowadays, we often hear the expressions, ‘network society’, and ‘information society’.

Keywords: Information and Communication Technology, Globalization, Global Economy, Economic Globalization and Social Globalization.

Résumé

Le monde d'aujourd'hui est devenu un «village global» et l'information et les communications circulent de manière transparente sans barrières de distance, d'espace et de temps. Cet article analyse les rôles théoriques et pratiques de la communication de l'information à travers les médias dans des contextes internationaux et mondiaux. Il examine également une variété de théories qui abordent les principes sous-jacents de la connectivité internationale au sein des propriétés des médias. L'article vise à indiquer le besoin d'articuler et d'apprécier les rôles théoriques et pratiques de l'information et de la communication des médias dans un contexte international et mondial. Les rôles théoriques et

pratiques des médias ont été choisis au hasard comme unité d'analyse. Les résultats montrent que l'information et la communication transfrontalières contribuent énormément aux sphères mondiales socioculturelles, politiques et économiques à plusieurs niveaux. L'économie mondiale est connectée, le commerce électronique et le commerce international ont progressé et les marchés financiers sont devenus plus liés. En plus, la culture populaire mondiale et de nouveaux types de sociétés ont émergé. De nos jours, nous entendons souvent les expressions telles «société en réseau» et «société d'information».

Mots-clés: Technologies de l'information et de la communication, mondialisation, économie mondiale, mondialisation économique et mondialisation sociale.

Introduction

The term “Global Village” was coined by the Canadian Media Scholar, Marshal McLuhan (1964) when he described it as being “a brand new world of all at oneness, time has ceased, and space has vanished”. Even more recently, the advent of New Media technologies including; Satellite, Internet, World Wide Web, Computers, have made the world shrink even smaller and cross-border engagements easier. Particularly, the internet has gained importance over the last few decades in terms of globalization hence, its huge role in the heightening of international flow of information. Basically, information and communication across borders contribute majorly to the socio-cultural, political, and economic global spheres in many ways. The world economy is connected, e-commerce and international trade have advanced, and financial markets have become more linked. Furthermore, global popular culture and new types of societies have emerged. Nowadays, we often hear the expressions, ‘network society’, and ‘information society’.

According to Cavanaugh and Mader (2002), Media globalization, International communication and sharing of information at the global stage is one that includes any device or application such as a computers, the internet, radio, television, telephone, and satellite. The media are the leading player in the process of globalization. In other words, the most important factors that have made globalization possible are the technological advancements made to information and communication systems. Owing to the advent of Information and Communication Technology, distances have shrunk and accessing information has become easier.

Meanwhile, Globalization is a field that has attracted a growing body of research in recent times. It has overtime been an area of discourse in different fora

considering the enormous role it plays in shaping the new global society. Traditionally, the definition of globalization focuses on economics and the effects of multinational corporations. In the book “Alternatives to Economic Globalization”, Cavanaugh and Mader (2002) highlighted other factors that are associated with globalization including; the displacement of traditional nation-states by global corporate bureaucracies, advancement of consumerism, privatization of public services, integration of national economies, global cultural homogenization, and corporate deregulation. Nonetheless, this paper focuses on practical roles of infusing technology into information, communication and media within a global context.

Practical Roles of Media Information and Communication in Global Context

Many scholars of media and politics have stressed the importance of media and evaluated them in a variety of ways. First, Boyd-Barrett and Rantanen (2001) share the opinion that global media has created a ‘global village’ where we can point to changes in the way citizens of states view themselves and others. The media as institutions supply information and at the same time shape people’s learning process about the world, thus mass media have correspondingly large influence on individuals’ picture of the world. In this context, local, national and international news agencies circulate information and images between countries, thus forming relationships between people from the local to the international level. Iyorza (2008) states that globalization permeates the political, economic and socio-cultural angles of every nation in the world today.

To prevent ambiguity and for easier understanding, the media roles in global contexts are subdivided into three categories:

- i. Economic,
- ii. Social and Cultural, and
- iii. Political.

A. Role of Media in the Economy

Economic globalization has become inevitable in recent times due to developments in technology (particularly the internet) which allows access to economic information within a short span of time. Schultz (2010) says without information technology, economic communication and information sharing at the global stage could not have taken place. In other words, platforms such as computers, World-Wide Web and the Internet have provided an online, safe, and sustainable network for the take-off and growth of economic globalization. As a result, a new informational networked global economy has emerged over the last few decades. Its informational features have increased the capacity of companies

or nations to provide and process knowledge-based information effectively. It is global and networked because a huge core of economic activities can now be handled on a global scale and through a global network (Castells, 2010).

Technology is the driving force behind this new economy. After the introduction of the internet, its “e” components became attached to a variety of economic activities and many processes of business became available in real time. The “new” definition embedded in the term “new economy” stems from this process. Economic activities powered by the media and technology are the central component of this new economic system (Damaskopoulos, 2004).

In this new economy, geographical distance has become less important and financial markets have become more transparent. Thus, media has helped the operations of stakeholders by providing an opportunity to monitor the performance of managers. Also, there is an increased transparency in pricing of goods and services through the ability to compare prices, as well as, in processing orders through instant tracking. For example, local SMEs (Small-Medium sized Enterprises) can display their products to customers in foreign countries through media platforms thus allowing them to search independently for the products (Damaskopoulos, 2004).

The emergence of the internet in 1994 for business purposes has also significantly improved supply chain processes. It would generally pose a really great problem to handle the pieces of any business through a single international supply chain. In addition, in the globalization process, economic growth has occurred and it is very clear that ICT has helped this growth by making global integration of the supply chain and finance possible. Moreover, business has become more efficient as a result of speed and low cost of transactions.

Similarly, Traditional firms have also started to use e-commerce because it is a direct and rapid way to reach customers (Capineri & Leinbach, 2004). Additionally, e-commerce has grown various businesses dramatically through expansion of reach and market. E-bay, Amazon, Konga and Jumia are good examples that showcase the success rate of these types of web based businesses. They operate mainly online and gather various manufacturers and distributors in one virtual zone. Hence, the location of the website (store) is no longer of much importance in the conduct of business (Schultz, 2010). Moreover, Schultz (2010: 38) argued that “with IT, the various parts of a sales transaction can easily be scattered across many states or many countries”.

Furthermore, financial trading between sellers and buyers, companies and salesmen and exchanges on the stock exchange have changed. This change affects not only the financial markets, but also the global economy because financial operations have become more interdependent on a global scale.

Economies are interdependent because financial markets are interconnected. Consequently, ICT is the most significant enabler of economic globalization; even though there are other enablers such as trade regulations and economic policies (Schultz, 2010). The new economy consists of informational, networked, and global components. Thus, e-commerce and international trade have advanced, and financial markets have become more connected.

B. Role of Media in Politics

As a fact of the 21st century, the evaluation of power is dependent on information, which is supplied through communication and mass media. Government departments, individual officials and ministers use mass media as direct channels to societies with the purpose of explaining policy to their nation and external publics. Therefore, the media seem to enable the evolution of the international society by distributing information that builds bridges between groups and individuals around the world.

In the new millennium, the politicians are aware that their governance performance locally and globally can be enhanced by the introduction of technology into various media platforms. For example, during the 8th legislative session, Senator Dino Melaye was active in deploying twitter to great advantage in spreading his thoughts to his constituents and national audience. Internationally, President Donald Trump has also used the new media technology to spread his message to American voters and admirers around the world.

Cohen (ibid: 52) noted that politicians use mass media in international negotiations in order to manipulate the international public space and other governments. It can be described as an indirect media impact that mainly depend on pressure from the government's supporters and interest groups that can result to policy change at the planning stage of a decision in foreign policy.

Similarly, media are pluralizing forces which work against power's ability to influence and control. Essentially, Boyd-Barrett and Rantanen (2001) opine that local, national and international news agencies circulate information and images between countries and form relationships between people from the local level to the international level. Global media have integrated its audiences in the reportage of wars, peace and in the diplomatic process. The global media's efforts to attract public attention bring the crises and conflicts to the top of the agenda to persuade audiences to influence government policies. At the same time, governments can also use media platforms to set their own agenda and to make their views known to the public.

As an agenda setting agent, the news media have an important job in defining issues, primarily to help the public understand the newest array of priorities and alliances. In this context, the news coverage can be useful for justifying state actions by shaping what people around the world think of it.

C. Role of Media in Social and Cultural Settings

Information, communication and media at the global stage have also affected the social and cultural dimensions of globalization. Cultures have been impacted by the introduction of cross cultural communication processes. Targowski (2009: 304) “The global culture is a patterned way of behaving under global conditions and processes, sustained by the exchange and flow of goods, people, information, knowledge, and images. These exchanges and flows give rise to communication processes that gain some autonomy on the global level.” Another area where the impact of new media is seen in journalism is in the rise of the blog and so-called blogosphere. This enables citizens to act as journalists, commentators, interpreters and distributors of news reports. Also, communications networks and organizations provide pedestals for text messaging, micro-blogging and blogging for the social and cultural campaigns which have a direct impact in the conduct of socio-political affairs.

Likewise, people can make social connections regardless of physical distance on a global scale. The reach of ICT which makes it possible to interact and communicate in new ways has led to the emergence of the network society (Uimonen, 2003). This networked society is a new form of community that has a certain linked basis and can interact with other communities online and in real time. As a result of this process, the internet has become the center of social activity for many.

The numbers of online shoppers are increasing, online banking is encouraged by banks, universities are commencing a new type of teaching - online teaching or distance learning -, and email is becoming a common communication method among people. These improvements show that the media have helped to create a new global pattern of social interactions. They provide interactions among people more easily and more effectively than ever before (Castells, 2010). In the context of the information age, the development of technology has made the information society a reality. Many disciplines have provided different approaches to explaining or defining the information society such as the mobile society, knowledge society, virtual society, and network society, and so on. These types of information oriented social actions and approaches are positive since informed people can become more knowledgeable and this is very important for the progression of civilization (Targowski, 2009).

In the network or information society, social movements have also been empowered by ICT. Communication has always been of importance to social movements. Traditional communication media, such as journals, publishing houses, and radio stations, have long been used by activists and groups to promote their causes. However, after the emergence of the internet, this became a means of direct and low cost communication with the public. As a result, the Internet has provided a tool for keeping different activists networked and organized. It has also enabled circulation of information, and has been used as a forum for protesting against an issue (Della Porta & Mosca, 2005). Thus, civil society has gained a new means of propagating its claims. Such movements have operated globally as a result of the effect of these improvements, with a number of protests occurring simultaneously in different countries.

Within the global justice movement, the internet has also been used for the dissemination of information, and as means of attracting the public interest on global issues. The donation of money for these social causes has become easier. Some other form of donations sites have emerged such as “Go Fund Me” which is widely used by people around the world, Nigeria inclusive. In addition, social movements have become global and more effective. For example, the recent conviction of Harvey Weinstein resulted from the global social movement—**#MeToo** that involved the naming and shaming of predators by victims of sexual assaults.

In summary, it can be argued that the introduction of technology into media processes have given it the power to affect ways of life, domestic politics, foreign policy decision-making and promoting the images of political actors. This is in line with Worugji’s argument that exposure to western education has exposed all to wider spectrum of knowledge including technological knowhow, (2007).The new media can also be used in building a global civil society, developing a new public sphere and political activism (De Jong et al. 2005).

Theoretical Perspectives in Media Information and Communication

Communication researchers have searched for theoretical basis to interpret various phenomena related to global mass media. Here are a variety of theoretical perspectives from scholars that are addressing these questions.

Modernization theory is a theory used to explain the process of modernization within societies. The theory was coined by Daniel Lerner becoming popular in the 1950s. Modernization theory is a description the processes of transformation

from underdeveloped societies to modern societies. It states that underdeveloped countries can be brought to development in the same manner more developed countries have. The basic purpose of modernization theory was that humans were able to change their society and this change was often facilitated by advancements in technology, production, and consumption. It states that through economic growth the changes in social, political, and cultural structures can be made.

Modernization theory points out that the underdeveloped countries should leave behind their historical agrarian lifestyles and adopt modern industrial or technological lifestyles. This new lifestyle would then enable them improve on their economic and social conditions.

In the modern age, modernization theory looks at how new technologies and systems are leading to a more homogenized world. It talks about the world of globalization, where cultural mores and ideas are easily spread throughout the world, leading to a sort of universal culture that serves as a baseline for all cultures. As societies in the world modernize technologically, cultures will also become more like one another. It can also help spread social ideals of greater liberty and freedom.

Cultivation Theory: George Gerbner (1977) has developed cultivation analysis theory. Gerbner's theory asserts that television has displaced traditional sources of socialization such as the family, the church, and school. The dominant communication agencies produce the message systems that cultivate the dominant image patterns. They structure the public agenda of existence, priorities, values, relationships. According to Gerbner, Gross, Morgan and Signorielli (1986), "television has become the primary common source of socialization and everyday information (mostly in the form of entertainment) of an otherwise heterogeneous population," Gerbner believed that mass media produced images from, "the mainstream of a common symbolic environment" (p. 18). Stephen Littlejohn (2002) commented that Gerbner's theory "is not a theory of individual media 'effects' but instead makes a statement about the culture as a whole". Gerbner predicted that heavy television viewers are far more likely to be socialized through television than light television viewers. Gerbner went on to describe what he called the "mean world syndrome" which suggests that the violent nature of television content will affect heavy television viewers to believe that the world is a violent place, where people cannot be trusted. In summary, cultivation research is concerned with the most general consequences of long-term exposure to centrally-produced, commercially supported systems of stories. Cultivation analysis concentrates on the enduring and common consequences of growing up and living with television. (Audience research, 2004)

Dependency Theory Dependency theory rejected the view of modernization theory. It argues that underdeveloped countries have unique features and structures of their own. Dependency Theory is a means to address the role of news agencies in the international distribution of news content. Oliver Boyd-Barrett and Terhi Rantanen (2002) discussed the roots of dependency theory as stemming from the viewpoint that agencies such as Reuters, were seen as significant in certain British territories during the 1930's as promoting British trade interests. It states that the developed countries are in the situation of being the weaker members in a world market economy and they are dependent on developed countries for their economic growth. The developing countries are continually fed by developing nations to improve their conditions. Dependency theory also posits that the degree of dependency increases as time goes on. Wealthy countries are able to use their wealth to further influence developing nations to increase their wealth.

Megaphone Effect Theory: Bloch and Lemish (2003) have created a new term which they call the megaphone effect. They theorize that cultural texts which become adopted into the popular culture in the United States can be transformed into a global cultural phenomenon, through the international media. The theory suggests a two-step process. First, cultural texts cross the Atlantic (or Pacific) and enter into the culture of the United States. The second step occurs when these texts are then perceived as having wider international appeal, and are then marketed and distributed to the global community. The study analyzed: television programs, news networks, children's culture, and pop music. It suggested that the adoption of local cultural texts into mainstream U.S. culture provided a greater opportunity for their voices to be heard on a global scale. This theory is quite new to the globalization literature and as yet there are few published articles on the subject.

In his book, *The Roar of the Crowd* (1993), Michael J. O'Neill viewed media globalization from the point of view of a news reporter. O'Neill attributed Margaret Thatcher's rise to political power as stemming from her television appearances in the 1974 election. O'Neill's main thesis is that mass communication, on a global scale, drives public opinion. His view of communication technology as a major force behind human organizations and political movements is similar to Marshall McLuhan's theory of technological determinism.

Tetrad Theory Perhaps one of the most interesting theories regarding media globalization is one developed by Marshall McLuhan and Bruce Powers (1989) in their book *The Global Village*. McLuhan and Powers present a model which

they refer to as a tetrad. The tetrad is a made up of three elements. The first element is visual space which refers to a Western civilization mind set, based on logical systematic, linear, and Platonic reasoning. The second element is acoustic space, which is more holistic and Asian in approach. The third element is the tetrad itself which is a collision of these two opposing philosophies in a four part metaphor, consisting of enhancement, reversal, retrieval and obsolescence. According to McLuhan and Powers, "The tetrad helps us to see both the positive and the negative results of the artifact" The example is given of the invention of the automobile which greatly aided the need for transportation, but also changed society by transforming workers into distant commuters, dooming the inner city to skyscraper landscapes, while at the same time creating the need for suburbs. The practicality of verifying tetrad theory with social science research seems limited since it seems to be as much a philosophy as a theory of communication. In any case, McLuhan and Power's work does offer a number of interesting and almost prophetic observations, considering that the book was written in 1989. Before the Internet existed, the authors describe the interactive nature of the World Wide Web. For example, the new telecommunication multi-carrier corporation, dedicated solely to moving all kinds of data at the speed of light, will continually generate tailor-made products and services for individual consumers who have pre-signaled their preferences through an ongoing data base. Users will simultaneously become producers and consumers.

Conclusion

Summarily, the theoretical and practical media information dissemination allows access to economic information within a short span of time and a huge core of economic activities can now be handled on a global scale and through a global network. They also explain policy to their nation and external publics. Therefore, media information seems to enable the evolution of the international society by distributing information that builds bridges between groups and individuals around the world. They also aid cross cultural communication processes and promote social connections. This paper has been able to discuss the social effects of the introduction of technology into the information, communications and media space and the changes it is bringing to the way society evolves. Through various theories, we are able to see that the media have a powerful effect on development. Politics, the economy, culture and inter-relationships are gradually changing as the media plays its role in practicalizing theoretical constructs. This will bring about new theories of development as members of society and the media become global players.

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